

Sterility percentage showed a high direct effect on grain yield (0.928). Direct negative effects were observed for number of panicles/m², panicle length, and 1,000-grain weight. Other characters, such as panicles/m² did not show any direct effect on yield.

Filled grains per panicle and sterility percentage appear to be the most reliable indices for selection under saline conditions. □

Yield and yield attributes of rice cultivar Mahsuri grown at different salinity levels in farmers' fields, Khambhat taluka, Gujarat, India.

Salinity level ^a	EC (dS/m)	ESP ^b	Panicles (no./hill)	Sterility (%)	Unfilled grains hill (g)	Dry filled grains/hill (g)	Straw/hill (g)	Biological yield/hill (g)	Harvest index
Normal	1.4	0.81	15	16.9	1.66	27.14	10.3	39.1	0.69
Low	6.3	4.6	5.4	10.3	1.35	8.2	10.3	19.1	0.40
Moderate	11.8	6.9	4.8	29.7	0.45	7.1	8.83	12.1	0.33
Severe	25.6	12.0	13.2	80.6	3.4	2.7	14.6	23.1	0.11
LSD (0.05)	9.1	6.8	4.9	50.6	1.64	9.9	4.3	12.6	0.13

^aCategorized by farmers. ^bExchangeable sodium percentage.

Performance of rice cultivar Mahsuri at different salinity levels

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In villages lying between 22°24' and 22°30' N and 72°25' and 72°37' E in

Khambhat taluka, Kheda district, Gujarat, India, soil degradation caused by waterlogging has resulted in rice becoming the principal crop. This has further aggravated the salinity problem and waterlogging. Cultivable fields have been affected by salinity. We collected soil samples and rice plants (Mahsuri) from saline-affected fields to see the effect of soil degradation on the crop.

Soil analysis showed that EC values

increased from 1.4 to 25.6 dS/m. The increased salinity caused a reduction in all rice yield parameters measured (see table). The biological yield under severe soil salinity was higher than under less salinity because of the increase in straw weight per hill. Sterility increased in response to increasing salinity. Salinity decreased economic yield by 70, 74, and 90% at EC of 6.3, 11.8, and 25.6 dS/m. □

Manifestation of heterosis in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in a saline environment

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We studied the expression and magnitude of heterosis in rice in a saline environment.

Five varieties and strains were crossed during 1982:

1. NIAB RICE (NR-I)/C23-3-1
2. NR-I/IR6
3. NR-I/Jhona 349

4. Jhona 349/IR6
5. IR6/Basmati 370

The F₁ and the parents were grown in NIAB fields in Jun 1983. Six-week-old seedlings were transplanted into drainable concrete field basins (6 × 6 × 1 m). For artificial salinization, 4 commercial salts — MgCl₂, NaCl, CaCl₂, Na₂SO₄—were mixed with soil at ratios of 1:4:5:10. Desired salinity was further achieved by infrequent irrigation with tubewell water (saline sodic). In the randomized complete block design with 4 replications, seedlings were transplanted at 1/hill and 20-cm

spacing. At least 20 plants/ replication were observed. Yield and 1,000-grain weight were recorded after drying grains to 14.0% moisture. To test the performance of F₁ hybrids, heterosis was calculated over that of the better parent.

Heterosis was variable and inconsistent not only for plant attributes but also for crosses (see table).

No heterosis was observed for number of primary branches per panicle and panicle fertility percentage in the saline environment.

The greatest heterosis for yield per

Heterosis estimates (%) in F₁ over better parents for yield and yield components of rice under salt stress.^a NIAB, Faisalabad, Pakistan, 1982.

Cross	Heterosis (%)								
	Plant height	Productive tillers plant	Panicle length	Primary branches/panicle	Grains/panicle	Total florets/panicle	Panicle fertility percentage	1000-grain weight	Yield per plant
NR-I/C23-3-1	+0.6*	-17.0**	-2.2	+7.5	+44.4**	+25.9**	-2.1	-1.6	+78.0**
NR-I/IR6	+5.1*	+6.3	+7.8**	+3.3	+25.3**	+30.9**	-7.6**	+8.9**	+87.5**
NR-I/Jhona 349	+3.2*	-25.0**	-1.7	-9.2	+16.5**	+4.1	-2.8	-3.7**	-30.0**
Jhona 349/IR6	+12.4**	+54.8**	+6.9**	+9.4	0.2	+34.4**	-33.9**	+19.7**	+154.4**
IR6/Basmati 370	-13.8**	-40.8**	-4.7**	+0.9	+20.4**	+13.6**	+0.3	+11.6**	+13.9**

^a* = significant at P=0.05, ** = significant at P=0.01. pH 9.0, E_c 6.5 dS/m at 25°C, sodium adsorption ratio = 22.2.